

ORIGINAL ARTICLE

Triple gains: More production, less nitrogen and greater diversity from cropland reallocation in England and Wales

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Funding information

European Commission, Grant/Award Number: 862357

Abstract

Agricultural production is the main driver of nitrogen pollution and diversity loss. This study assesses the potential of cropland reallocation to simultaneously increase production and decrease nitrogen balances, and its impact on crop diversity. Our technological specification extends the by-production approach by dynamically modelling the impact of the N balance from the previous year on current year crop production. We use a robust order-m data envelopment analysis to estimate the production frontier, and the Hill-Shannon index to assess crop diversity before and after optimal cropland reallocation. The application uses Farm Business Survey data from farms in England and Wales between 2015 and 2019. The results show that efficiency gains would have increased crop production by GBP 10.31 per ha and decreased the nitrogen balance by 1.05 kg per ha, when compared with a business-as-usual scenario. Reallocation, only focusing on increasing production, would have increased crop production by GBP 83.74 per hectare and reduced the nitrogen balance by 2.01 kg per ha. Reallocation, focusing on increasing production and decreasing the nitrogen balance, would have increased the former by GBP 71.88 per hectare and reduced the latter by 4.99 kg per ha. The median cropland diversity increases by approximately 0.24 species per farm in both reallocation scenarios. Our results suggest that farmers can simultaneously improve economic and environmental performance, which would increase crop diversity. Effective policies should address

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barriers to diversification and foster management practices that both increase production and decrease nitrogen balances.

KEYWORDS

crops, data envelopment analysis, diversity, efficiency, nitrogen, reallocation

JEL CLASSIFICATION

C61, D22, Q15, Q50

1 | INTRODUCTION

Agricultural production is the main driver of nitrogen (N) pollution and diversity loss, with these two factors transgressing planetary boundaries (Campbell et al., 2017; Steffen et al., 2015). In croplands, over half of the applied N is lost to the environment (Gu et al., 2023; Lassaletta et al., 2020). Conventional agricultural practices have significantly narrowed the diversity of cultivated species. From a range of over 50,000 edible plants, only 15 species provide 90% of the world's energy intake. Among these, rice, maize and wheat provide about two-thirds of the global caloric consumption (Gruber, 2017). This reduced diversity has increased vulnerability to extreme weather events, pests and diseases, all of which are expected to increase with climate change (FAO, 2017). Meanwhile, the global population and demand for food are still increasing (FAO, 2017). As a result, increasing food production, reducing N pollution and increasing diversity have become a major challenge for agricultural policy (Kanter et al., 2020; Pe'er et al., 2019).

Soil N balances can be positive, leading to pollution, or negative, decreasing future production. In crop production, N balances are mainly positive due to two factors. First, excess N is a non-point source pollutant, impacting the environment rather than the farm. Second, farmers often overapply fertilisers as a strategy to mitigate the risk of potential shortfalls in crop production. The economic and behavioural reasons behind this overapplication are well-documented (Del Rossi et al., 2023; Paulson & Babcock, 2010; Sheriff, 2005). Given crop-specific N demands, it is important to understand the relationship between cropland allocation, production and N balances. Studies show that improving farm management can decrease N balances without production losses (Gu et al., 2023; Lamkowsky et al., 2021). Furthermore, reallocating cropland offers opportunities to increase production and decrease N balances.

Cropland reallocation has been identified as an important source for increasing agricultural production and decreasing its environmental impact (Adamopoulos & Restuccia, 2022; Beyer et al., 2022; Folberth et al., 2020). Cropland reallocation, defined as the optimisation of crop choices within a farm or a region, not only affects potential production and N balances but also determines crop diversity. Crop diversity refers to the richness and evenness of crops grown within an area. Several studies have found synergies between increasing production and increasing crop diversity (Tamburini et al., 2020). Additionally, synergies exist between increasing crop diversity and decreasing N balances through practices such as crop rotation (Renwick et al., 2019), planting cover and catch crops (Renwick et al., 2019; Valkama et al., 2015) and intercropping (Bedoussac et al., 2015; Gaudin et al., 2015; Pelzer et al., 2014). Despite these findings, the potential for cropland reallocation to increase production and decrease N balances, along with its consequences for crop diversity, remains unexplored. Our study addresses this gap by explicitly examining *what* should be grown, through cropland allocation, and *how* it should be grown, through efficiency improvements.

Our research contributes in two ways. First, we examine the potential of cropland reallocation for simultaneously increasing production and decreasing N balances, and its consequences for crop diversity. Previous studies in production economics have explored the potential of cropland reallocation for mitigating greenhouse gas emissions (Wang et al., 2023) and reducing pesticide use (Kahindo & Blancard, 2022). The relationship between cropland reallocation, production and diversity has also been covered by Ang et al. (2018). However, the specific impacts of cropland reallocation on production and N balances, as well as its implications for crop diversity, have not been investigated. To some extent, this issue is addressed by Folberth et al. (2020), who analysed the global effects of cropland allocation focusing on production and the impacts on N fertilisers, but without explicitly targeting the reduction of N balances. Their study focuses on yields, which ignores inputs other than land in the production process and potential efficiency gains (Coelli et al., 2005). Our study addresses this gap by explicitly modelling the production relationship between inputs, outputs and N balances. This approach provides a clearer understanding of the role of cropland reallocation in production and N balances.

Second, we consider the dynamic impact of N balances on crop production. This aspect is often overlooked in empirical production economics (Kuosmanen, 2014; Kuosmanen & Kuosmanen, 2013). Unlike previous research, which models N balances statically, we introduce a more realistic dynamic model of crop production, where the N balance from the previous period serve as an input for the production in the current period. Although N is highly mobile, there is a dynamic effect from fertiliser applications and crop choices of previous years (Grant et al., 2016). For instance, N from organic sources releases more slowly and improves water retention and overall nutrient availability (Gutser et al., 2005; Smith et al., 2015). Our modelling approach captures the impact of potentially beneficial N management practices (Gu et al., 2023), by considering how the quality and quantity of N applied in the previous period affect crop production in the current period.

Our empirical application focuses on English and Welsh crop farms for the years 2015–2019. This sample is a suitable candidate for a case study, since N and diversity are currently prioritised in agricultural policy and regulation in the United Kingdom (Bateman & Balmford, 2018; DEFRA and EA, 2022). The significance of these factors has grown, given the need to develop new agricultural policies following Brexit (Smith et al., 2023). We use a robust order- m data envelopment analysis (DEA) approach (Cazals et al., 2002), which mitigates the impact of atypical observations in the frontier estimation. Our technological specification extends the by-production approach of Murty et al. (2012) by dynamic modelling of N balances in crop production and allowing for optimal cropland reallocation. In our model, the N balance from the previous year serve as an input for the crop production of the current year.

We assess three scenarios where efficiency and cropland reallocation can increase production and decrease N balances. First, without reallocation, we focus on efficiency improvements to simultaneously increase production and decrease N balances (BAU + YN). Second, with reallocation, we examine the increase in production (RLC + Y). Third, also with reallocation, we consider the simultaneous increase in production and decrease in N balances (RLC + YN). Comparing RLC + YN and RLC + Y reveals the opportunity cost of reducing N balances. Finally, we investigate the impact of these two reallocation scenarios (RLC + Y and RLC + YN) on crop diversity.

The remainder of this paper is as follows. The first part of Section 2 presents the theoretical framework on the technological properties of crop production and N balances. In the remaining parts of Section 2, we describe the data and our empirical approach for assessing the potential of cropland reallocation to increase crop production and decrease N balances. Section 3 reports the main findings of our study, which are subsequently discussed in Section 4. Section 5 addresses limitations and directions for further research. Section 6 concludes.

2 | METHOD

2.1 | Production technologies

Following Murty et al. (2012), we distinguish between two types of sub-technologies, one for the production of intended crop outputs and another one for the unintended production of N balances. The Environmental Zones (EnZs) (Metzger et al., 2005), shown in Figure 1, define the edaphoclimatic context for these production technologies.

The sub-technology of crop outputs (\mathcal{T}_{zt}) for the environmental zone $\mathbf{z} \in \mathbb{R}^Z$ at time $\mathbf{t} \in \mathbb{R}^T$ is defined by:

$$\mathcal{T}_{zt} = \{(\mathbf{x}_{czt}, x_{fzt}, \mathbf{x}_{vzt}, b_{zt-1}, y_{azt}, y_{szt}) \in \mathbb{R}^{C+V+4}: \mathbf{x}_c, \mathbf{x}_f, \mathbf{x}_v, \text{ and } b_{t-1} \text{ can produce } \mathbf{y}_a \text{ and } \mathbf{y}_s\}, \quad (1)$$

where the inputs are the farm land use areas of selected crops ($\mathbf{x}_{czt} \in \mathbb{R}_+^C$), fertiliser expenses ($x_{fzt} \in \mathbb{R}_+^1$), other agricultural inputs ($\mathbf{x}_{vzt} \in \mathbb{R}_+^V$) and N balances ($b_{zt-1} \in \mathbb{R}^1$) from previous year. We provide the details on the estimation of the N balances in Farm level estimation of N balances: Appendix. The outputs are the aggregated crop ($y_{azt} \in \mathbb{R}^1$) and livestock ($y_{szt} \in \mathbb{R}^1$) outputs. \mathcal{T}_{zt} takes the classical assumptions of closedness, convexity, free disposability of inputs and outputs and variable returns to scale (Banker et al., 1984). Accounting for edaphoclimatic differences that affect the possibilities for agricultural production and N losses, we separately estimate production technologies for the EnZs Atlantic North (ATN) and Atlantic Central (ATC) (Metzger et al., 2005). In addition, we control for interannual weather variability by only considering observations from the same year t in the estimation. We treat the N balance from the previous year as an input for the production of the current year. This dynamic approach addresses the limitations

FIGURE 1 Environmental zones (Metzger et al., 2005) in England and Wales – classification based on NUTS 2 (The Nomenclature of Territorial Units for Statistics (NUTS) classification is a territorial division based on national administrative divisions. The NUTS 2 level consists of regions suited for the application of regional policies; Eurostat, 2015) regions.

of previous studies that only characterise N balances as static (Kuosmanen, 2014; Kuosmanen & Kuosmanen, 2013).

The sub-technology of N balances (\mathcal{N}) for the EnZ z at time t is defined by:

$$\mathcal{N}_{zt} = \{(\mathbf{x}_{czt}, x_{fzt}, b_{zt}) \in \mathbb{R}^{C+2}: \mathbf{x}_c \text{ and } \mathbf{x}_f \text{ can produce } b_t\}, \quad (2)$$

where cropland uses (\mathbf{x}_{czt}) and fertiliser expenses (x_{fzt}) define the production of N balances ($b_{zt} \in \mathbb{R}^1$). The overall technology defining the by-production relationship is given by the intersection between \mathcal{T} and \mathcal{N} . Following Murty et al. (2012), the disposability assumptions in \mathcal{N} are different than the ones in \mathcal{T} . The disposability assumptions in \mathcal{N} ensure that there is a minimal and efficient level of N balances. Formally, for a given level of \mathbf{x}_{czt} and x_{fzt} there is minimum level of b_{zt} , thus if $b'_{zt} \leq b_{zt} \rightarrow (\mathbf{x}_{czt}, x_{fzt}, b'_{zt}) \in \mathcal{N}_{zt}$. Higher fertiliser use (x_{fzt}) is assumed to increase the N balance, *ceteris paribus*: $x'_{fzt} \geq x_{fzt} \rightarrow (\mathbf{x}_{czt}, x'_{fzt}, b_{zt}) \in \mathcal{N}_{zt}$. However, for land use (\mathbf{x}_{czt}), the

larger the area, *ceteris paribus*, the greater the opportunity to decrease the N balances via crop production: $\mathbf{x}'_{czt} \leq \mathbf{x}_{czt} \rightarrow (\mathbf{x}'_{czt}, x_{fzt}, b_{zt}) \in \mathcal{N}_{zt}$. Hence, land is a N-mitigating input in our model. This is also motivated by the fact that there is a negative balance for the combined effect of air deposition, leaching and volatilisation in the United Kingdom (Ludemann et al., 2024). This modelling approach differs from Hoang and Coelli (2011), Serra et al. (2014) and Ait Sidhoum et al. (2020), which treat land as an N-generating input.

2.2 | Scenarios

We use three scenarios to assess the impact of efficiency and cropland reallocation on crop production and N balances. First, without reallocation, the scenario ‘business-as-usual with increased efficiency’ (BAU+YN) maximises crop production and minimises N balance. Second, with reallocation, the scenario ‘reallocation for production’ (RLC+Y) focuses on maximising crop production. Third, also with reallocation, the scenario ‘reallocation for production and N’ (RLC+YN) maximises crop production and minimises N balance. By comparing business-as-usual (BAU) and BAU + YN, we assess the potential for efficiency improvements to simultaneously increase production and decrease N balance. By comparing BAU + YN and RLC + Y, we assess the maximum potential of cropland reallocation for increasing production. By comparing RLC + Y and RLC + YN we assess potential opportunity cost between N and crop production. In the context of these scenarios, we compute the potential production and N values for each farm based on production frontier estimates. We use DEA (Banker et al., 1984; Charnes et al., 1978) to empirically envelop the frontier encompassing the intersection between \mathcal{T}_{zt} and \mathcal{N}_{zt} . In what follows, we further investigate the production frontier projections for each farm in scenarios BAU + YN (Section 2.3), RLC + Y and RLC + YN (both in Section 2.4).

2.3 | Efficiency improvements without reallocation

We first investigate the extent to which farms can increase crop output and decrease N balances without reallocation (BAU + YN). We do this by solving a DEA model for every farm k in year t in each EnZ z as follows:

$$\max_{\lambda, \mu, \alpha, \beta} (\alpha + \beta) \quad (3)$$

s. t.

$$\sum_{k=1}^{K_z} \lambda_{kt} \mathbf{x}_{ckt} \leq \mathbf{x}_{ct} \quad (3.1)$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^{K_z} \lambda_{kt} x_{fkt} \leq x_{ft} \quad (3.2)$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^{K_z} \lambda_{kt} \mathbf{x}_{vkt} \leq \mathbf{x}_{vt} \quad (3.3)$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^{K_z} \lambda_{kt} b_{kt-1} \leq b_{t-1} \quad (3.4)$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^{K_z} \lambda_{kt} y_{akt} \geq y_a + \alpha \quad (3.5)$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^{K_z} \lambda_{kt} y_{skt} \geq y_{st} \quad (3.6)$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^{K_z} \lambda_{kt} = 1 \quad (3.7)$$

$$\lambda_{kt} \geq 0 \quad (3.8)$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^{K_z} \mu_{kt} \mathbf{x}_{ckt} \leq \mathbf{x}_{ct} \quad (3.9)$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^{K_z} \mu_{kt} x_{fkt} \geq x_{ft} \quad (3.10)$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^{K_z} \mu_{kt} b_{kt} \leq b_t - \beta \quad (3.11)$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^{K_z} \mu_{kt} = 1 \quad (3.12)$$

$$\mu_{kt} \geq 0 \quad (3.13)$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^{K_z} \lambda_{kt} \mathbf{x}_{ckt} = \sum_{k=1}^{K_z} \mu_{kt} \mathbf{x}_{ckt} \quad (3.14)$$

$$\alpha \geq 0 \quad (3.15)$$

$$\beta \geq 0 \quad (3.16)$$

α represents the potential to increase crop production, and β the potential to decrease N balance for each farm under evaluation. Here, K_z is the total number of observations in EnZ z . The *lambdas* (λ) are the intensity weights linked with \mathcal{T}_{zt} and the *mus* (μ) are those linked with \mathcal{N}_{zt} .

Constraint (3.14) equalises the cropland allocation in both sub-technologies, as cropland use is endogenous in the model. It is somewhat similar to the dependence constraint of Dakpo (2015) and Lozano (2015), which equalises the optimal values of polluting inputs in both sub-technologies. However, we permit optimal levels of other inputs to differ in both

technologies. In line with Murty and Russell (2020), such a specification still leads to projected levels of output and N that fall within the intersection of the crop and the N sub-technologies. Additionally, as α and β are independent, both frontier projections are efficient in the respective sub-technologies. As a result, our specification seeks for optimal cropland reallocation, while imposing minimal assumptions consistent with our theoretical framework.

We apply the robust order- m DEA approach developed by Cazals et al. (2002) to mitigate the impact of atypical observations and unrealistic frontier projections. For the subset of inefficient farms in which $\alpha > 0$ or $\beta > 0$, we draw M random samples with replacement taking 70 percent of the observations, by which all observations in the subsample have an equal or better performance than the farm under assessment. After solving the DEA problem $M = 1000$ times, we have for every farm observation the following robust frontier projections:

$$y_a^* = y_a + \frac{1}{M} \cdot \sum_{m=1}^M \alpha_m \tag{4}$$

and

$$b^* = b - \frac{1}{M} \cdot \sum_{m=1}^M \beta_m, \tag{5}$$

which we also use in the next steps of cropland reallocation.

2.4 | Efficiency improvements through cropland reallocation

Figure 2 conceptually illustrates the process of cropland reallocation, showing how the reallocation affects the distribution of two hypothetical crops (A and B) within a farm. This process influences both production and nitrogen balances, with potential implications for crop diversity.

We estimate the inefficiencies associated with cropland reallocation by modifying the DEA model presented in Equation (3) to include cropland uses as decision variables. To isolate the crop allocation component, the reallocation model uses the optimal values previously found for crop production using Equation (4) and N balances using Equation (5). We do this for the two reallocation scenarios, $o = \{(\text{RLC} + \text{Y}), (\text{RLC} + \text{YN})\}$, by solving a DEA model for every farm k in year t in each EnZ z as follows:

$$\begin{cases} \max \alpha^o, & \text{if } o = \text{RLC} + \text{Y} \\ \lambda, \mu, \alpha^o, \\ \mathbf{x}_{ct}^o, b_t^o \\ \\ \max \alpha^o + \beta^o, & \text{if } o = \text{RLC} + \text{YN} \\ \lambda, \mu, \alpha^o, \\ \beta^o, \mathbf{x}_{ct}^o \end{cases} \tag{6}$$

s. t.

$$\sum_{k=1}^{K_z} \lambda_{kt} \mathbf{x}_{ckt} \leq \mathbf{x}_c^o, \quad c \in [1, C'] \tag{6.1}$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^{K_z} \lambda_{kt} \mathbf{x}_{ckt} \leq \mathbf{x}_{ct}, \quad c \in]C', C] \tag{6.2}$$

FIGURE 2 Conceptual representation of the cropland reallocation problem. Two optimisation scenarios are considered: (1) increasing production and (2) simultaneously increasing production while reducing nitrogen balances. The example illustrates how reallocation can alter the area of two hypothetical crops (A and B) within a farm, potentially influencing crop diversity.

$$\sum_{k=1}^{K_z} \lambda_{kt} x_{fkt} \leq x_{ft} \quad (6.3)$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^{K_z} \lambda_{kt} x_{vkt} \leq x_{vt} \quad (6.4)$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^{K_z} \lambda_{kt} b_{kt-1} \leq b_{t-1} \quad (6.5)$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^{K_z} \lambda_{kt} y_{akt}^* \geq y_{at}^* + \alpha^o \quad (6.6)$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^{K_z} \lambda_{kt} y_{skt} \geq y_{st} \quad (6.7)$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^{K_z} \lambda_{kt} = 1 \quad (6.8)$$

$$\lambda_{kt} \geq 0 \quad (6.9)$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^{K_z} \mu_{kt} x_{ckt} \leq x_{ct}^o, \quad c \in [1, C'] \quad (6.10)$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^{K_z} \mu_{kt} x_{ckt} \leq x_{ct}, \quad c \in]C', C] \quad (6.11)$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^{K_z} \mu_{kt} x_{fkt} \geq x_{ft} \quad (6.12)$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^{K_z} \mu_{kt} b_{kt}^* \leq \begin{cases} b_t^o, & \text{if } o \text{ is RLC+Y} \\ b_t^* - \beta_t^o, & \text{if } o \text{ is RLC+YN} \end{cases} \quad (6.13)$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^{K_z} \mu_{kt} = 1 \quad (6.14)$$

$$\mu_{kt} \geq 0 \quad (6.15)$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^{K_z} \lambda_{kt} \mathbf{x}_{ckt} = \sum_{k=k_z}^{K_z} \mu_{kt} \mathbf{x}_{ckt} \quad (6.16)$$

$$\sum_{c=1}^{C'} \mathbf{x}_{ck_o t} = \sum_{c=1}^{C'} \mathbf{x}_{ct}^o \quad (6.17)$$

$$\alpha^o \geq 0 \quad (6.18)$$

$$\beta^o \geq 0, \quad \text{if } o \text{ is RLC+YN} \quad (6.19)$$

where \mathbf{x}_c^o are the cropland uses that are reallocated in each scenario. In constraints (6.1) and (6.10), we only allow reallocation for the most representative crops, $c \in [1, C']$ (see details in Section 2.6). Constraint (6.17) guarantees that the total land use is kept constant after reallocation.

2.5 | Crop diversity analysis

The results of our reallocation model have implications for farm-level crop diversity. To measure crop diversity, we use the Hill-Shannon index (Hill, 1973). The Hill-Shannon index (HSI) can be interpreted as the ‘effective number of cropland uses’. HSI is the exponential of the Shannon index. Its mathematical expression is given by

$$\text{HSI}_{kt} = \exp\left(-\sum_{c=1}^{C_H} L_{ckt} \times \ln L_{ckt}\right), \quad (7)$$

where L_c is the proportion occupied by land use c out of C_H land uses (see details in Section 2.6). We calculate crop diversity at the farm and aggregated (England and Wales, and EnZs) levels. The HSI formulation rewards species richness and evenness of crops grown within an area. This formulation allows us to express the crop diversity in units of species (Roswell et al., 2021). We are mainly interested in the changes of HSI comparing the scenarios before and after optimal reallocation. To obtain a statistical interpretation of changes in HSI, we compute bootstrapped confidence intervals (Efron & Tibshirani, 1986) and conduct permutation tests (Richter & McCann, 2007). In the bootstrapped approach, we assess the difference in median diversity within the 5th and 95th percentiles by resampling the dataset 1000 times and calculating the median HSI for each resample. This forms the 95% confidence intervals. In the permutation test, we evaluate the statistical significance of the observed median HSI difference by randomly shuffling scenarios and performing 10,000 permutations. A p -value is calculated to determine whether the observed difference is statistically significant. It indicates whether the changed impact of crop reallocation on diversity is due to chance. In Appendix, we present the details and results (Table A1) of these statistical approaches.

TABLE 1 Variables description and units.

Variable	Description and units
$x_{ckt} \in \mathbb{R}^{10}$	Crop areas [ha]: of which nine ($C' = 9$) can be reallocated – linseed, barley, beans, beets, oats, peas, potatoes, rapeseed and wheat. The 10th area (C) is classified as ‘Other crops with N removal’
$x_{fkt} \in \mathbb{R}^1$	Fertiliser use expenses [GBP 2019]
$x_{vkt} \in \mathbb{R}^6$	Other agricultural inputs: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other land uses [ha] • Unpaid labour [h] • Depreciation [GBP 2019] • Livestock costs [GBP 2019] • Livestock feed [GBP 2019] • Other variable costs [GBP 2019]
$b_{kt} \in \mathbb{R}^1$ and $b_{kt-1} \in \mathbb{R}^1$	Nitrogen balances [kg of N] at year t and $t - 1$, respectively
$y_{akt} \in \mathbb{R}^1$	Crop output [GBP 2019]
$y_{skt} \in \mathbb{R}^1$	Livestock output [GBP 2019]

2.6 | Data

The Farm Business Survey (FBS) (Duchy College, 2019a, 2019b, 2020, 2022a, 2022b) is the dataset from which we extract farm level inputs and outputs for the period of 2015 until 2019. Table 1 describes the input variables and output variables introduced in Equations (1) and (2).

We select the reallocation crops (C') based on their representativeness and availability of N coefficients. We extract the N removal and fixing coefficients per crop from the International Plant Nutrition Institute (2013) and Ludemann et al. (2024). To identify the most representative crops, we divide England and Wales into four major regions aggregating the official regions.¹ We select nine crops for potential reallocation based on the availability of N coefficients and the criterion that each crop must have at least 1 year with 15 farms producing it in the four major regions. In the FBS, several crops are presented at a subspecies level. We aggregate them at the species level due to their similar growing conditions, nitrogen characteristics and the absence of subspecies-specific nitrogen data in our sources. For example, beets (*Beta vulgaris*) include sugar beet, beetroot and beet tops. This aggregation simplifies the analysis while maintaining agronomic consistency. Crops with N removal coefficients used by fewer farms are aggregated and categorised under ‘Other crops with N removal’. Although these ‘Other crops with N removal’ contribute to the N balance equations, they are not considered for reallocation. The category ‘Other land uses’ under ‘Other agricultural inputs’ includes all other agricultural areas lacking N removal coefficients, predominantly representing pastureland. For the crop diversity analysis, we use these 11 different land uses classes (C_H).

We deflate monetary values to 2019 values using price indices from Eurostat (2022). The variable ‘Other variable costs’ aggregates expenses related to seeds and young plants, electricity, total

¹To reduce the number of divisions we aggregate the official regions into North-East (NE – “North East”, and “Yorkshire & the Humber”), North-West (NW – “North West”, “West Midlands”), South-East (SE – “South East”, “East Midlands”, “London”, and “East of England”), and South-West (SW – “South West”, and “Wales”). These official regions are related to the farm structural surveys, which are given at the highest tier of sub-national division in England (DEFRA, 2023) and Wales (StatsWales, 2023).

heating fuel, crop protection, energy, paid labour and other crop costs. The variable ‘Livestock costs’ aggregates veterinary expenses and other veterinary costs. We compute implicit quantities for these variables using Törnqvist price indices (Balk, 2008: 72).

We focus on farms primarily engaged in agricultural activities by excluding farms where non-agricultural output exceeds 33% of total output (i.e., crops, livestock and non-agricultural outputs). We exclude farms that have fertiliser costs without associated N quantities. We also exclude farms that produce crop output without a designated area. Furthermore, we only include farms listed in the FBS that are present for at least two consecutive years, as our dynamic specification requires N balances from two consecutive years.

We use sample weights to adjust our sample to accurately represent the farm structure of each of the four main regions (NW, NE, SW and SE) mentioned earlier. Each farm observation receives a weight defined by

$$w_{kt} = \sum_{p=1}^P \left(\frac{\text{FarmArea}_{pt}}{\sum_{p=1}^P (\text{FarmArea}_{pt})} \cdot \frac{\text{RegionArea}_{pt}}{\text{SampleRegionArea}_{pt}} \right) \quad (8)$$

where each weight w indicates how representative each farm k is based on the crops it grows, relative to the overall crop distribution in the region, at year t . The term FarmArea_{pt} represents the area occupied by each crop $p \in \mathbb{R}^P$ at each farm and year. The RegionArea_{pt} is area occupied by crop p at year t in each region, sourced from the farm structure reports provided by DEFRA (2023) for England and StatsWales (2023) for Wales. The $\text{SampleRegionArea}_p$ is the total area occupied by crop p at year t in our sample of the FBS. We introduce p as a new notation for crop area because the farm structure reports groups beans and peas together. For $p \in [1, P']$, the crop groups include barley, field beans and peas, maize, oats, rapeseed, potatoes and wheat. For all other land uses, such as $p \in [P' + 1, P]$, we assume that the inverse of the sampling intensity $\left(\frac{\text{RegionArea}_{pt}}{\text{SampleRegionArea}_{pt}} \right)$

equals the average observed for the P' crops. Finally, by considering the weight of each farm, we compute crop production, N balances and crop diversity for England and Wales and for each EnZ, as presented in the Results section.

The resulting sample is representative of farms in England and Wales, where many farms combine crop and livestock activities. Since the analytical focus is on crop production, we control for the livestock component by including variables such as livestock costs, feed and output. Excluding farms with livestock would reduce the sample size and limit the representativeness of the analysis. In the empirical application using DEA, the consideration of livestock variables ensures that the farms are compared with peers with similar levels of livestock importance. This accounts for heterogeneity in N balances associated with livestock activities that interact with cropland (e.g., N fertilisation of pastures and N exports through grazing).

Our sample consists of English and Welsh farms for the period of 2015 until 2019. There are on average 542 observations per year. The average farm size is 210 hectares for the full sample, 225 hectares for ATC and 171 hectares for ATN. Table 2 presents the descriptive statistics of the farm level inputs and outputs encompassing all years. Table A2 in Appendix details the sample size per year and EnZs.

3 | RESULTS

3.1 | Comparison between efficiency and reallocation models

Our results show that the studied sample of English and Welsh farms can simultaneously increase crop production and decrease N balances by efficiency gains and optimal cropland reallocation. Removing inefficiency without cropland reallocation (BAU + YN) can on average

increase crop production from 905.17 GBP 2019 per ha to 915.48 GBP 2019 per ha and decrease the N balance from 41.93 kg per ha to 40.88 kg per ha. Henceforth, we express all monetary values in GBP 2019 terms. Although the first reallocation scenario (RLC + Y) only focuses on increasing production, it also suggests a potential reduction in N balances. In this scenario, the maximum potential crop output is 988.91 GBP per ha and the minimum potential N balance is 38.87 kg per ha.

The second reallocation scenario (RLC + YN) focuses on the simultaneous increase in crop production and decrease in N balance. In this scenario, the maximum potential crop output is 977.05 GBP per ha and the minimum potential N balance is 33.88 kg per ha. As a result, including the objective of reducing N balance reveals an opportunity cost of 2.37 GBP per kg of N. In what follows, we present these results highlighting the differences between the EnZs ATC and ATN.

Figure 3 shows the average potential crop output in each scenario. Comparing Figure 3b,c, the potential for increasing production is greater for ATC than for ATN in all scenarios. However, this distinction becomes less pronounced in relative terms with respect to the BAU scenario.

Figure 4 shows the average potential reduction in N balances in each scenario. Comparing Figure 4b,c, the N balance per ha is higher in ATN than in ATC. However, in relative terms,

TABLE 2 Descriptive statistics of farm level inputs and outputs – yearly averages and standard deviation between parentheses, without weights.

Variables	England and Wales	Atlantic Central (ATC)	Atlantic North (ATN)
Linseed area (ha)	0.7 (4.6)	0.9 (5.3)	0.2 (1.6)
Barley area (ha)	28.2 (49.7)	30.3 (56.8)	23.1 (23.8)
Beans area (ha)	5.3 (14.3)	6.0 (15.5)	3.6 (10.6)
Beets area (ha)	5.9 (23.1)	8.1 (26.9)	0.4 (4.3)
Oats area (ha)	5.0 (15.0)	5.1 (16.1)	4.7 (11.7)
Peas area (ha)	3.0 (13.6)	4.0 (15.8)	0.6 (3.8)
Potatoes area (ha)	3.9 (18.9)	4.2 (21.0)	3.2 (11.9)
Rapeseed area (ha)	17.1 (31.1)	20.1 (34.5)	9.7 (18.3)
Wheat area (ha)	60.8 (84.7)	72.5 (94.1)	31.9 (43.1)
Other crops with N removal (ha)	8.9 (42.5)	10.9 (49.6)	3.7 (11.8)
Other land uses (ha)	79.1 (89.6)	73.4 (87.6)	93.1 (92.7)
Unpaid labour (h)	946.7 (1385.7)	941.1 (1425.0)	960.7 (1283.8)
Depreciation (GBP 2019)	48,477.9 (66,092.3)	52,178.7 (74,510.8)	39,299.8 (36,298.6)
Livestock feed (GBP 2019)	58,661.6 (184,740.1)	56,311.1 (188,459.9)	64,491.3 (175,155.3)
Livestock costs (GBP 2019)	20,161.1 (36,222.0)	17,969.8 (37,072.0)	25,595.8 (33,430.3)
Variable costs (GBP 2019)	119,077.7 (324,978.8)	141,531.7 (378,801.2)	63,389.7 (85,870.1)
Fertiliser costs (GBP 2019)	26,763.7 (31,825.2)	29,394.9 (35,408.0)	20,238.1 (18,879.9)
Crop output (GBP 2019)	204,960.9 (417,333.8)	243,431.7 (476,205.3)	109,549.4 (176,175.6)
Livestock output (GBP 2019)	137,426.1 (326,102.2)	127,433.1 (335,069.7)	162,209.8 (301,496.9)
Nitrogen balance – previous year (kg)	9025.7 (25,269.0)	8277.4 (28,687.5)	10,881.5 (13,292.7)
Nitrogen balance (kg)	8653.8 (27,255.9)	7725.9 (31,103.7)	10,955.2 (13,380.5)
Observations	542	386	156

FIGURE 3 Average potential crop output for each scenario from 2015 to 2019 in (a) England and Wales, (b) Atlantic Central and (c) Atlantic North. Scenarios: Business-as-usual without cropland reallocation (BAU); business-as-usual, without cropland reallocation, maximising production and minimising N balance (BAU + YN); with cropland reallocation and maximising production (RLC + Y) and with cropland reallocation, maximising production and minimising N balance (RLC + YN).

the proportional reductions in ATN are smaller than those in ATC, unlike in the crop production results. Consequently, farms in the ATC produce on average more crop output per kg of N than those in ATC. The potential increases in production for scenario RLC + Y also reduce N balances in both EnZs. This pattern is consistent except for 2017 in ATN, when the optimal production level was associated with an increase in N balance. For completeness, we present the annual results for crop production and N balances in [Appendix](#) (Table A3).

The difference in output between the reallocation scenarios represents the opportunity cost of aiming to reduce N balance while also aiming to increase production. [Figure 5](#) shows the annual estimates of these opportunity costs. Our results suggest that the opportunity costs for the farms in ATC are greater than for those farms in ATN. This pattern occurs in all years except for 2019. In that year, the opportunity cost is 2.31 GBP per kg in ATN and 1.77 GBP per kg of N in ATC.

FIGURE 4 Average potential N balance for each scenario, from 2015 to 2019, in (a) England and Wales, (b) Atlantic Central and (c) Atlantic North. Scenarios: Business-as-usual without cropland reallocation (BAU); business-as-usual, without cropland reallocation, maximising production and minimising N balance (BAU + YN); with cropland reallocation and maximising production (RLC+Y) and with cropland reallocation, maximising production and minimising N balance (RLC+YN).

3.2 | The potential impact of optimal cropland reallocation on crop diversity

We now analyse how optimal cropland reallocation changes the Hill-Shannon index for crop diversity. We first present the results at the farm level and later at the aggregate level. [Figure 6](#) shows how optimal cropland reallocation would change the distribution of farm level Hill-Shannon index. Before reallocation, the median farm in England and Wales has an effective number of species of 3.13. After optimal cropland reallocation, the median diversity would increase to 3.37 species in RLC+Y and to 3.36 species in RLC+YN. The increases in diversity are greater in ATC (0.24 species for RLC+Y and 0.23 species for RLC+YN) than in ATN (0.15 species for RLC+Y and 0.14 species for RLC+YN).

The distributions of farm diversity are very similar for the scenarios of RLC+Y and RLC+YN. In [Appendix \(Table A1\)](#) we present the annual median farm level diversity for

FIGURE 5 Opportunity costs (GBP 2019 per kg of N) of reducing N in cropland reallocation scenarios from RLC+Y to RLC+YN in (a) England and Wales, (b) Atlantic Central and (c) Atlantic North. The costs are calculated as the ratio between the output difference and the reduction in N, comparing the scenarios RLC+Y (maximising production) and RLC+YN (maximising production and minimising N balance).

England and Wales and for each EnZ separately. It also describes the details on the bootstrapping procedure and permutation test. The results from bootstrapped and permutation tests for the medians show that the RLC+YN in general led to a lower diversity than the ones observed at RLC+Y. We observe a small median difference of 0.01 species for England and Wales. Although the permutation test indicates that the medians differ statistically, there is a consistent overlap over the years between the bootstrapped confidence intervals of the medians.

In Table 3, we present the Hill-Shannon diversity at the aggregated level for England and Wales, and the EnZs, separately. In England and Wales, the diversity change become less pronounced when compared with the differences observed at the farm level. However, for ATC the difference between RLC+Y and RLC+YN becomes larger. Similarly to the farm-level results, the diversity in ATC exceeds that in ATN.

FIGURE 6 Hill-Shannon diversity (HSI), or effective number of cropland uses, at the farm level. Weighted density distribution before and after reallocation – vertical lines represent the group medians. (a) England and Wales, (b) Atlantic Central and (c) Atlantic North. Scenarios are business-as-usual without cropland reallocation (BAU), maximum production allowing for cropland reallocation (RLC+Y) and maximum production and minimum N balance allowing for cropland reallocation (RLC+YN).

3.3 | Cropland use changes

We further analyse the changes in cropland use for the reallocation scenarios of RLC+Y and RLC+YN. In [Figure 7](#), we show these changes in percentage points relative to the available area for reallocation. For the scenario RLC+Y, optimal cropland allocation would have led to an increase in beets (+0.79%), potatoes (+0.45%), rapeseed (+0.33%), peas (+0.15%) and linseed (+0.03%) and a decrease in barley (−1.18%), oats (−0.34%), beans (−0.15%) and wheat (−0.07%). For the scenario RLC+YN, optimal cropland reallocation would have led to an increase in

TABLE 3 Hill-Shannon diversity (HSI), or effective number of cropland uses, at the aggregate level for England and Wales, and for the Environmental Zones (EnZs) Atlantic Central (ATC) and Atlantic North (ATN).

Region	Year	BAU	RLC + Y	RLC + YN
England and Wales	2015	5.35	5.35	5.40
	2016	5.24	5.32	5.40
	2017	5.72	5.74	5.77
	2018	5.85	5.99	6.01
	2019	5.67	5.71	5.80
	All	5.57	5.63	5.69
Atlantic Central (ATC)	2015	5.57	5.56	5.64
	2016	5.52	5.65	5.74
	2017	6.11	6.12	6.17
	2018	6.22	6.40	6.41
	2019	6.02	6.07	6.19
	All	5.90	5.97	6.04
Atlantic North (ATN)	2015	4.10	4.09	4.09
	2016	3.94	3.94	3.93
	2017	4.07	4.09	4.07
	2018	4.35	4.36	4.37
	2019	4.17	4.19	4.18
	All	4.14	4.15	4.14

Note: Scenarios are business-as-usual without cropland reallocation (BAU), maximum production allowing for cropland reallocation (RLC + Y) and maximum production and minimum N balance allowing for cropland reallocation (RLC + YN).

linseed (+0.88%), beets (+0.62%), potatoes (+0.27%), rapeseed (+0.27%) and peas (+0.02%) and a decrease in barley (−0.89%), oats (−0.45%), wheat (−0.45%) and beans (−0.27%). Nevertheless, there is some heterogeneity between ATC and ATN.

The importance of each crop depends on the EnZ and scenario considered. Optimal cropland allocation would imply a reduction in barley land across all scenarios and zones, yet it shows a greater decline under RLC + Y compared with RLC + YN. Linseed area increase is particularly important for ATC under the RLC + YN. For the other crops, there is some variation depending on the year and scenario. Notable changes under RLC + Y include a decrease in barley of −1.13% in ATC and −1.39% in ATN, contrasted by increases in rapeseed of +0.27% in ATC and +0.64% in ATN; while wheat shows opposite results depending on the EnZ, it decrease by −0.21% in ATC and increases by +0.58% in ATN. For the RLC + YN scenario, there is a decrease in barley by −0.88% in ATC and −0.94% in ATN, while rapeseed demonstrates an increase of +0.24% in ATC and of +0.44% in ATN. In Appendix (Figure A1), we present the observed yearly variation.

4 | DISCUSSION

The aim of this study is to assess the extent to which cropland reallocation can simultaneously increase crop production and decrease N balances, and its implications for crop diversity. In line with other studies, our study finds that there is scope to reduce inefficiency through land reallocation (Adamopoulos & Restuccia, 2022; Ang et al., 2018; Ang & Kerstens, 2016). Overall, our study suggests that the sample of English and Welsh crop farms can simultaneously increase

FIGURE 7 Cropland use changes in percentage points relative to the available area for reallocation in (a) England and Wales, (b) Atlantic Central and (c) Atlantic North.

crop production and reduce N balance through optimal cropland reallocation. This optimal cropland reallocation would also enhance crop diversity. These results can be compared with other studies that find a similar association between increasing crop production and reducing N balances (Gray Betts et al., 2023; Gu et al., 2023; Tamagno et al., 2022), increasing crop production and increasing diversity (Ang et al., 2018; Donfouet et al., 2017; Tamburini et al., 2020) and reducing N balances and increasing diversity (Duchene et al., 2017; Pelzer et al., 2014; Zhang et al., 2015).

If there are synergies between increasing crop production, decreasing N balance and diversifying crops, why have farmers not taken advantage of them? Addressing the information gaps, policy limitations and market forces that disincentivise crop diversity could be crucial.

As farmers are typically risk averse (Bowman & Zilberman, 2013), one would expect them to use crop diversity to reduce their risk exposure. However, the empirical evidence is mixed. Some studies suggest that risk averse behaviour leads to diversification (Slijper et al., 2020), while others do not (Hellerstein et al., 2013; Van Winsen et al., 2016). This discrepancy may stem from limited knowledge about the economic benefits of diversification, which impedes informed decision making, along with other factors such as additional labour demand and management complexity (Ang et al., 2018; Bowman & Zilberman, 2013; Sánchez et al., 2022; Van Winsen et al., 2016). Moreover, the influence of market power and structure, such as the mutual dependence between farmers and large food processors, dictates crop choices (Sexton & Xia, 2018). Additionally, subsidies for specific crops may further incentivise specialisation (Di Falco & Perrings, 2005). In summary, exploring the synergies between increasing production and reducing N balance, requires effectively addressing the information gaps about the benefits of crop diversity, overcoming management difficulties, understanding market forces and reforming policies that disincentivise crop diversity.

Behavioural aspects may also explain inefficiency in production and N. In our results, the potential decrease in N balance exceeds the potential increase in crop production in relative terms. This happens especially in the scenarios BAU + YN and RLC + YN, which consider the simultaneous increase in crop production and decrease in N balance. This may be connected to N pollution being characterised as a non-point source pollutant. That is, the negative effects of N pollution materialise predominantly far from the polluting farms. Additionally, in response to loss aversion, farmers often apply fertilisers beyond the economic optimum as a risk mitigation strategy (Del Rossi et al., 2023; Pannell, 2017; Sheriff, 2005).

There is potential for farmers to simultaneously increase production and N efficiencies, as indicated by scenario BAU + YN. Cost-effective farm management practices that could increase crop production and decrease N balances are detailed in Gu et al. (2023). These practices include precision agriculture, the '4R nutrient stewardship' approach (right fertiliser type, right amount, right placement and right time), optimised crop rotation and allocation, genetic improvement (detailed in Han et al. (2015)), optimal irrigation and soil conservation measures.

Our study suggests that decreasing N would decrease crop production, as illustrated by the comparison between the scenarios RLC + Y and RLC + YN. These results are in line with those in Dakpo et al. (2023), Shaik et al. (2002) and Mandrini et al. (2022), which suggest that abating N is costly in agriculture. Our results also suggest that the magnitude of these trade-offs may depend on the edaphoclimatic context, which calls for targeted farm management and policy recommendations.

Our findings indicate that certain crops can simultaneously increase production and decrease N balances in varying degrees. Comparing our results with Ang et al. (2018), who focused on dynamic profit maximisation for crop farms in the East of England from 2007 to 2013, we find some points of agreement. Our results align with theirs in projecting increases for beets and peas, and decreases for beans and wheat in the ATC EnZ, the predominant EnZ in the East of England. However, we observe different trends for potatoes, barley and oats. Consistent with Ang et al. (2018), we observe some annual variability, likely driven by market and weather factors, emphasising the importance of these factors in crop allocation decisions.

The incorporation of environmental zones in this study mitigates the problem of agronomic and environmental heterogeneity. Nevertheless, some heterogeneity persists at the micro level, encompassing market conditions and fine-scale edaphoclimatic variability. While EnZ-specific technologies address edaphoclimatic differences across EnZs, the feasibility of reallocating crops within zones often diverges between agronomic and economic dimensions. For example, in the case of sugar beet, most processing facilities are located in the East Midlands and East of England, predominantly within the ATC zone. Other regions, such as the West Midlands, London, South East and South West, also fall within the ATC zone. On average, sugar beet is transported 45 km from field to factory (NFU, 2021). Although sugar beet cultivation might

be agronomically viable in the South West, the cost of transporting the crop to processing facilities in the East would pose economic challenges. Consequently, a detailed understanding of both micro-level edaphoclimatic conditions and local market dynamics is critical for refining the applicability of our findings.

Comparing results between ATC and ATN requires cautious consideration due to differences in frontier estimation. Our results suggest that the potential for increasing crop production and decreasing nitrogen balances is relatively lower in ATN than in ATC, but these differences must be interpreted carefully. We use EnZ-specific production frontiers to reflect distinct agronomic and environmental conditions. Alternatively, a meta-frontier analysis could assess all farms against a common benchmark, theoretically allowing direct comparisons across EnZs. However, this approach would assume uniform edaphoclimatic conditions across England and Wales, which may be unrealistic, especially in crop production. As we discussed in this section, even assuming homogeneity within each EnZ may ignore other sources of unobserved heterogeneity. Extending this assumption to the whole of England and Wales would exacerbate these issues. Nevertheless, using EnZ-specific frontiers also comes with trade-offs. For instance, the smaller sample size in ATN compared with ATC likely results in a more conservative frontier estimation for ATN. This partially explains the observed lower potential for improvement in ATN. EnZ-specific frontiers are essential for accurately capturing agronomic and environmental differences, which is important for the assessment of management efficiency and crop reallocation. However, they limit the direct comparability of results between EnZs.

Our analysis indirectly reflects the potential influence of crop rotations and cropping sequences through two mechanisms: N dynamics and benchmarking. The dynamic effect of N balances considers the influence of previous rotations and sequences on residual N availability, partially capturing the role of crop rotations and sequences in N dynamics. In the benchmarking approach, farms adopting rotations and sequences that enhance productivity are positioned closer to the efficient frontier. Thus, while rotations and sequences are not explicitly modelled, the efficiency scores indirectly reflect the potential benefits of these practices.

Our results suggest that farmers can simultaneously improve economic and environmental performance by crop diversification. Farmers have imperfect information about market and weather conditions, which may result in suboptimal cropland allocation. At the same time, crop diversification is one approach to reduce risks related to market and weather uncertainties (Renard et al., 2023; Renard & Tilman, 2019). Due to the positive relationship between risks and economic returns, using diversification to reduce risks could come at the expense of economic returns. Nevertheless, we observe that current diversity levels are below optimal, both economically and environmentally.

5 | LIMITATIONS AND DIRECTIONS FOR FURTHER RESEARCH

High dimensionality and potential unobserved heterogeneity may pose limitations for the empirical analysis. Comparing the different scenarios, our results indicate a relatively small potential for increasing crop production and reducing N balances without reallocation (BAU + YN scenario). The high dimensionality of our model may partly explain these conservative results. In DEA, increasing the number of variables and constraints tends to reduce the number of inefficient farms (Fried et al., 2008). Allowing for reallocation reduces the dimensionality problem by relaxing constraints. However, unobserved heterogeneity in local edaphoclimatic conditions or other local constraints, may impede effective cropland reallocation in practice. Nevertheless, we mitigate this issue by controlling for heterogeneity in edaphoclimatic conditions when considering different technologies per year and EnZ, using a robust DEA approach.

Access to additional data can improve the accuracy in the estimation of N balances. Due to a lack of data, we do not account for deposits from irrigation, seeds and rainfall. However, deposits from rainfall are partially controlled by using annual technologies. Other factors that influence N balances, such as air deposition, leaching and volatilisation are implicitly considered. Due to our specification of \mathcal{N}_{zp} , these factors are considered constant depending on the EnZ and year, but also scaled due to the consideration of land uses. Our approach is more conservative compared with other studies that treat these factors as fixed constants across entire countries or regions (Ludemann et al., 2024; Zhang et al., 2015). Nevertheless, such factors can vary by local edaphoclimatic conditions (Tamagno et al., 2022). We used fixed coefficients for crop N fixation and removal; however, these can vary with genetic diversity, timing of harvest and other variables (Oenema et al., 2003). Therefore, further research using detailed data could refine our models to explore the interactions between crop choices, soil differences, management decisions and genetic varieties.

The relationship between crop allocation, crop production and N balances, could be further explored to include other species, levels, scales and modelling approaches. Our results are valid for farms cultivating the specific crops we allowed for reallocation. While we have selected crops that are representative for the crop sector in England and Wales, including a broader range of crops might lead to different outcomes. The observed higher farm-level crop diversity in our study may be partially related to rotational or sequencing diversity. Farms with diverse crop portfolios may have greater flexibility to adopt rotations and sequences at the field level, potentially influencing N dynamics and crop productivity. While the dynamic effect of N balances from the previous year reflects some of this relationship, its full extent cannot be confirmed due to data limitations. The absence of field-level data in the FBS limits our ability to directly model rotations and sequences or isolate their effects. Future research should rely on field-level data on crop rotations and sequences to more precisely evaluate their impacts on nitrogen balances, crop production and efficiency. Our results suggest increases in crop diversity at the farm and regional levels. However, in our models, diversity is an implication, rather than an objective. Additionally, exploring different levels of diversity, such as functional and temporal, along with varying scales (e.g., from field to landscape), could uncover novel relationships. This could prove valuable to farmers and policymakers who are interested in understanding how different scales and levels of diversity interact with crop production and N balances.

Further studies could use our models to include livestock, investigate circularity aspects and assess differences in the quality of N fertilisers. We have focused on arable crop production to mitigate additional uncertainties involved in including livestock, particularly those from estimating N content in feed and animal products. However, when data limitations are resolved, similar methods can also be applied to explore N issues in livestock production, as demonstrated by Lamkowsky et al. (2021). Additionally, including livestock enables the implementation of network models that connect livestock and crop production, as illustrated by Wang et al. (2023). These models can help further understanding of the relationship between agricultural production and N balances. In this light, interesting avenues for future research include the study of input self-sufficiency and the differences between organic and synthetic N sources. Our model can be readily adapted to include livestock enterprises in particular and farm circularity in general.

6 | CONCLUSION

This study investigates the issue of increasing crop production and decreasing N balance from a crop allocation perspective. We model the dynamic effect of the N balance from the previous year on crop production in the current year. We analyse data from 909 farms in England and

Wales between 2015 and 2019, resulting in 2711 observations across two environmental zones. Our application combines several state-of-the-art methods in non-parametric estimation of production frontiers. We estimate an efficient frontier by a robust DEA approach that is less sensitive to extreme values. Using a by-production framework, we model separate technologies for crop production and N balances. Doing so allows us to assess the potential of efficiency gains and cropland reallocation to increase crop production and decrease N balances.

We find that both efficiency and cropland reallocation can simultaneously increase crop production and reduce N balances, with reallocation offering greater benefits while also increasing diversity. Specifically, efficiency improvements may result in a 10.31 GBP per ha increase in crop production and a 1.05 kg per hectare reduction in N balances compared with a business-as-usual scenario. Meanwhile, the first reallocation scenario, initially focused on increasing production, also achieved a reduction in N balances, with increases of 83.74 GBP 2019 per ha in crop production and decreases of 2.01 kg per ha in N balances. However, including the objective of reducing N balances in the reallocation model revealed a trade-off, with crop production increasing by 71.88 GBP 2019 per ha and N balances decrease by 4.99 kg per ha. Thus, resulting in an opportunity costs of 2.37 GBP 2019 per kg of N between the reallocation objectives. Before reallocation, the median farm in England and Wales has an effective number of species of 3.13. After reallocation, number of cropland uses increases by ~0.24 species on both scenarios. Our analysis also shows variations across different years and environmental zones. Moreover, the high dimensionality and potential unobserved heterogeneity within our data may affect our estimates. Thus, it is important for farmers and policymakers to consider these limitations when interpreting our results.

Policymakers need to simultaneously address the issues of N pollution and specialisation in agriculture. Further research is needed to explore how these issues interact with diversity across multiple levels (e.g., farm, region, country and landscape) and scales (e.g., spatial, temporal and functional). Our results indicate synergies between increasing production, decreasing N balance and greater crop diversity at the farm level. It is important to address existing information gaps and path dependencies in supply chains, particularly regarding behavioural and management challenges that prevent farmers from exploiting these synergies. For example, by engaging educational and extension services to support and inform about the benefits of the '4R nutrient stewardship' (right fertiliser type, right amount, right placement and right time) and better crop allocation. Moreover, our research encourages further exploration of cropland reallocation, considering other dimensions such as intra-species diversity, temporal variations, different scales and their interactions.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was supported by the European Commission (Horizon 2020, grant 862357, project MIXED). The funding source had no influence on contents or submission of this document. Please note that this document reflects only the authors' views and that the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains. The authors gratefully acknowledge the UK Data Service for providing access to the Farm Business Survey (FBS) data.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

None of us have any relevant material or financial interests that could pose a conflict of interest with respect to the subject matter of our research.

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

We are unable to share the data from the Farm Business Survey due to data protection agreements. However, access to the dataset may be granted by the United Kingdom Data Service upon request.

ETHICS STATEMENT

Our study does not involve any ethical concerns related to human subjects.

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How to cite this article: Almeida-Furtado, M., Meuwissen, M.P.M. & Ang, F. (2025) Triple gains: More production, less nitrogen and greater diversity from cropland reallocation in England and Wales. *Journal of Agricultural Economics*, 00, 1–32. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1111/1477-9552.12625>

APPENDIX

Farm level estimation of N balances

We calculate the N balances (b_{kt}), for each farm $k \in \mathbb{R}^K$, at time t , as follows:

$$b_{kt} = q_{ekt} - \sum_{d=1}^D (\alpha_{dkt}^{RMV} - \alpha_{dkt}^{FIX}) \cdot \mathbf{q}_{dkt} \quad (\text{A1})$$

where $q_{ekt} \in \mathbb{R}^1$ represents the quantity of N in fertilisers applications (including organic), $\alpha_{dkt}^{RMV} \in \mathbb{R}^D$ is the coefficient describing the quantity of N removal per quantity of crop produced, $\alpha_{dkt}^{FIX} \in \mathbb{R}^D$ is the coefficient describing the quantity of N fixed per quantity of crop produced and $\mathbf{q}_{dkt} \in \mathbb{R}^D$ is the quantity of crop $\mathbf{d} \in \mathbb{R}^D$ produced by the farm. Due to our specification of \mathcal{N}_{zt} factors such as N deposition, leaching and volatilisation are implicitly considered (i.e. considered constant depending on the EnZ and year, but also scaled due to the consideration of land uses), which is in line with multiple studies that used fixed coefficients ($\text{N} \cdot \text{area}^{-1} \cdot \text{year}^{-1}$) for these factors at country or regional levels (Ludemann et al., 2024; Zhang et al., 2015).

Hill-Shannon index confidence intervals and permutation tests

To rigorously assess the impact of crop reallocation on changes in the Hill-Shannon index, we implement bootstrapped confidence intervals (Efron & Tibshirani, 1986) and permutation tests (Richter & McCann, 2007). In the bootstrap approach, we resample the original dataset 1000 times with replacement, adjusting the probability of selection based on sample weights attributed to each farm. For each resample, we calculate the median HSI. With the resampled medians, we calculate the 5th, 50th and 95th percentiles, which allows us to form 95% confidence intervals. In the permutation tests, we assess the statistical significance of observed median difference in HSI two scenarios. This involves randomly shuffling the scenarios under

comparison. The p -value is computed based on the proportion of permuted results where the permuted differences are as extreme as or more extreme than the observed difference. If the original difference exceeds the 95th percentile of the permuted differences, it suggests that the impact of reallocation on crop diversity is statistically significant at the 5% level. We do 10,000 permutations to ensure the reliability of results. This permutation test validates the impact of reallocation on crop diversity without relying on assumptions about the underlying data distribution (Table A1).

Detailed sample size and the percentage of inefficient observations

Yearly results for the improvements of crop output and nitrogen balances in the regions

Yearly results of cropland use changes

When assessing the crop changes in the scenarios RLC+Y and RLC+YN, we observe a consistent positive influence on both production and N levels across all years for beets (ATC), potatoes (ATC) and wheat (ATN). Conversely, there is a negative relationship for both production and N in barley (ATC and ATN). An exception is noted in linseed (ATC), which generally shows a negative relationship with production and a positive relationship with N. The inclusion of N as a reallocation objective increases the area of barley (ATC, ATN) and linseed (ATC), whereas wheat (ATC) shows a negative relationship (Figure A1).

TABLE A1 Hill-Shannon index confidence intervals and permutation tests for the medians.

Region	Year	Median confidence interval						Permutation test					
		BAU			RLC+Y			BAU, RLC+Y	BAU, RLC+Y	RLC+Y, RLC+Y			
		5%	50%	95%	5%	50%	95%	5%	50%	95%			
England and Wales	2015	2.96	3.07	3.21	3.10	3.24	3.40	3.09	3.21	3.39	0.162 (<0.001)	0.140 (<0.001)	-0.023 (<0.001)
	2016	2.80	2.94	3.12	2.96	3.20	3.41	2.94	3.20	3.38	0.262 (<0.001)	0.262 (<0.001)	0.000 (1.000)
	2017	2.92	3.09	3.25	3.13	3.29	3.43	3.09	3.27	3.43	0.199 (<0.001)	0.179 (<0.001)	-0.021 (<0.001)
	2018	3.18	3.35	3.46	3.47	3.60	3.68	3.46	3.58	3.67	0.246 (<0.001)	0.227 (<0.001)	-0.019 (<0.001)
	2019	3.11	3.25	3.41	3.42	3.54	3.65	3.40	3.54	3.64	0.288 (<0.001)	0.282 (<0.001)	-0.006 (<0.001)
All	3.05	3.13	3.19	3.29	3.37	3.43	3.29	3.37	3.42	0.239 (<0.001)	0.234 (<0.001)	-0.006 (0.010)	
ATC	2015	2.99	3.16	3.27	3.18	3.31	3.49	3.18	3.31	3.44	0.148 (<0.001)	0.147 (>0.001)	-0.000 (0.893)
	2016	3.01	3.21	3.33	3.28	3.48	3.58	3.30	3.47	3.58	0.269 (<0.001)	0.256 (>0.001)	-0.013 (>0.001)
	2017	3.14	3.31	3.44	3.40	3.49	3.63	3.40	3.51	3.66	0.187 (<0.001)	0.205 (<0.001)	0.018 (0.001)
	2018	3.46	3.57	3.66	3.75	3.85	4.04	3.72	3.83	3.98	0.281 (<0.001)	0.261 (<0.001)	-0.020 (0.022)
	2019	3.47	3.58	3.65	3.70	3.79	3.89	3.69	3.78	3.89	0.203 (<0.001)	0.196 (>0.001)	-0.007 (0.002)
All	3.26	3.33	3.38	3.51	3.56	3.62	3.50	3.55	3.61	0.229 (>0.001)	0.227 (>0.001)	-0.001 (>0.001)	

TABLE A1 (Continued)

Region	Year	Median confidence interval						Permutation test					
		BAU			RLC+Y			RLC+YN					
		5%	50%	95%	5%	50%	95%	5%	50%	95%	BAU, RLC+Y	BAU, RLC+YN	RLC+Y, RLC+YN
ATN	2015	2.39	2.74	3.25	2.45	2.74	3.25	2.45	2.74	3.25	0.000 (1.000)	0.000 (1.000)	0.000 (1.000)
	2016	1.81	1.95	2.26	1.81	2.14	2.76	1.81	2.00	2.72	0.190 (<0.001)	0.043 (<0.001)	-0.146 (>0.001)
	2017	2.03	2.28	2.77	2.18	2.50	2.80	2.18	2.49	2.80	0.216 (>0.001)	0.213 (>0.001)	-0.004 (0.104)
	2018	2.23	2.43	2.69	2.34	2.54	2.83	2.32	2.51	2.83	0.109 (<0.001)	0.081 (<0.001)	-0.028 (0.144)
	2019	2.16	2.44	2.61	2.25	2.54	2.69	2.23	2.54	2.64	0.105 (<0.001)	0.105 (<0.001)	0.000 (1.000)
	All	2.24	2.39	2.55	2.39	2.54	2.64	2.39	2.53	2.63	0.151 (<0.001)	0.138 (<0.001)	-0.013 (0.105)

Note: Scenarios: Business-as-usual without cropland reallocation (BAU); with cropland reallocation and maximising production (RLC+Y) and with cropland reallocation, maximising production and minimising N balance (RLC+YN).

TABLE A2 Detailed sample size and the percentage of inefficient observations.

Region	Year	Number of observations	% Of inefficient observations		
			BAU + YN	RLC + Y	RLC + YN
England and Wales	2015	366	4.1%	19.9	21.9
	2016	475	5.1	31.2	32.4
	2017	548	3.8	27.0	28.6
	2018	666	9.2	33.0	37.1
	2019	656	8.5	29.3	33.1
	All	2711	6.5	28.8	31.5
ATC	2015	292	4.8	24.7	27.1
	2016	341	4.7	34.9	34.9
	2017	387	3.4	28.2	31.0
	2018	459	7.8	37.7	40.5
	2019	453	6.4	33.3	34.4
	All	1932	5.6	32.3	34.2
ATN	2015	74	1.4	1.4	1.4
	2016	134	6.0	21.6	26.1
	2017	161	5.0	24.2	23.0
	2018	207	12.1	22.7	29.5
	2019	203	13.3	20.2	30.0
	All	779	8.9	20.2	25.0

Note: Scenarios: Business-as-usual without cropland reallocation, maximising production and minimising N balance (BAU + YN); with cropland reallocation and maximising production (RLC + Y) and with cropland reallocation, maximising production and minimising N balance (RLC + YN).

TABLE A3 Yearly results of crop output and nitrogen balances.

Region	Year	Crop output (GBP 2019 per ha)				Nitrogen balance (kg per ha)			
		BAU		Δ (BAU + YN, RLC + Y)		BAU		Δ (BAU + YN, RLC + Y)	
		BAU	Δ (BAU + YN, RLC + Y)	BAU + YN	Δ (RLC + Y, RLC + YN)	BAU	Δ (BAU + YN, RLC + Y)	BAU + YN	Δ (RLC + Y, RLC + YN)
England and Wales	2015	885.86	5.33	38.34	-9.92	35.36	-0.62	-0.41	-3.93
	2016	906.17	7.05	80.98	-13.58	59.76	-0.83	-2.62	-4.69
	2017	827.49	6.91	65.41	-16.85	38.89	-0.66	0.79	-6.21
	2018	913.29	19.41	108.09	-9.01	46.69	-1.69	-5.29	-5.07
	2019	997.28	13.44	75.22	-9.64	27.75	-1.51	-2.62	-5.08
ATC	2015	935.67	6.62	46.78	-12.30	32.09	-0.75	-0.48	-4.85
	2016	993.19	7.34	95.38	-16.61	56.42	-0.96	-2.35	-4.88
	2017	917.03	6.72	71.54	-15.51	30.48	-0.57	-0.65	-5.55
	2018	1015.09	22.48	126.50	-10.14	39.98	-1.69	-6.76	-5.19
	2019	1107.39	14.21	83.67	-9.23	18.58	-1.62	-2.71	-5.21
ATN	2015	680.50	0.00	3.54	-0.11	48.85	-0.06	-0.10	-0.15
	2016	611.40	6.05	32.21	-3.29	71.08	-0.38	-3.55	-4.02
	2017	537.65	7.54	45.58	-21.21	66.08	-0.94	5.45	-8.37
	2018	598.89	9.94	51.24	-5.53	67.41	-1.71	-0.73	-4.71
	2019	662.65	11.11	49.51	-10.86	55.61	-1.16	-2.34	-4.71

Note: Scenarios: Business-as-usual without cropland reallocation (BAU); business-as-usual without cropland reallocation, maximising production and minimising N balance (BAU + YN); with cropland reallocation and maximising production (RLC+Y) and with cropland reallocation, maximising production and minimising N balance (RLC+YN).

FIGURE A1 Boxplots of yearly cropland use changes in (a) England and Wales, (b) Atlantic Central and (c) Atlantic North. Scenarios: with cropland reallocation and maximising production (RLC+Y) and with cropland reallocation, maximising production and minimising N balance (RLC+YN).